

The SEIMS integrates the water and carbon cycle processes within a watershed based on the spatially-explicit framework, which can be categorized into four types: hydrology, soil erosion, terrestrial carbon cycle, and aquatic carbon cycle (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Processes represented in the SEIMS.

1.1 Hydrological Processes

1.1.1. Potential Evapotranspiration

In the SEIMS model, the potential evapotranspiration is calculated using the Penman-Monteith (PM) equation, which was proposed by Dutch meteorologist L. Penman and British agricultural engineer J.L. Monteith (Allen et al., 1989; Monteith, 1965). This equation comprehensively accounts for various factors such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, and radiation, providing a solid theoretical foundation and high computational accuracy.

$$PET = \frac{0.408\Delta \cdot (R_n - G) + \gamma \cdot \frac{900U_2 \cdot (e_s - e_a)}{T + 273}}{\Delta\gamma \cdot (1 + 0.34U_2)} \quad \text{Eq. (A.1)}$$

Where R_n represents the net radiation at the surface ($\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$), G is the soil heat flux ($\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$), e_s is the saturation vapor pressure, which can be calculated using the Goff-Gratch equation, and e_a is the actual vapor pressure, defined as the product of relative humidity and e_s . Δ denotes the slope of the saturation vapor pressure curve ($\text{kPa } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$), and γ is the psychrometric constant ($\text{kPa } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$), which is influenced by atmospheric pressure. U_2 is the wind speed at 2 meters height (m s^{-1}), and T is the air temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$).

1.1.2. Snow Pack/Glacier Snowmelt

The SEIMS model determines precipitation as rain or snow according to the daily average temperature. If the daily average temperature is below the critical temperature (typically set to 0°C), precipitation is considered as snow. It is assumed that the snow cover area and snow depth follow a natural logarithmic relationship, with a snow depth threshold defined. When the snow depth exceeds this threshold, snow is considered to completely cover the simulated unit. This threshold is influenced by various factors, such as vegetation, wind direction, slope orientation, etc., and can be defined by the user.

The calculation of snowmelt is based on the snowpack temperature, the daily maximum temperature, and the threshold of snowmelt temperature (Neitsch et al., 2011).

$$R_{SNO} = B_{milt} \cdot SNO_{cov} \left[\frac{T_{sno} + T_{max}}{2} - T_{milt} \right] \quad \text{Eq. (A. 2)}$$

Where R_{SNO} represents the amount of snowmelt (mm), T_{sno} is the snowpack temperature (°C), T_{max} is the daily maximum temperature (°C), and B_{milt} is the snowmelt factor (mm °C⁻¹ day⁻¹), which indicates the increase in amount of snowmelt for 1°C change in temperature. SNO_{cov} refers to the snow cover fraction. The snowmelt factor varies between its maximum value (at the summer solstice) and minimum value (at the winter solstice):

$$b_{milt} = \frac{(b_{milt6} + b_{milt12})}{2} + \frac{(b_{milt6} - b_{milt12})}{2} \cdot \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{365} \cdot (d_n - 81)\right) \quad \text{Eq. (A. 3)}$$

Where b_{milt6} is the melt factor for the day (mm °C⁻¹ day⁻¹), b_{milt6} is the melt factor for June 21 (mm °C⁻¹ day⁻¹), and b_{milt12} is the melt factor for December 21 (mm °C⁻¹ day⁻¹). d_n represents the day number of the year.

For simulation units defined as glaciers, the glacier mass balance depends on snowfall and glacier melt. The calculation of glacier melt is based on the temperature-index model (Gao et al., 2020): If snow covers the glacier, energy is first used to melt snow. Only when all the snow has melted, does the glacier begin to melt. The glacier melt equivalent (M_g , mm day⁻¹) is calculated as follows:

$$M_g = \begin{cases} F_{DD} C_g C_a T, & T > 0 \text{ and } SNO_{cov} = 0 \\ 0, & T \leq 0 \text{ or } SNO_{cov} > 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 4)}$$

Where F_{DD} represents the degree-day factor of glacier, C_g is the glacier melt factor, C_a is the slope aspect factor, and T is the daily average temperature.

1.1.3 Canopy interception

The interception refers to the portion of precipitation that is intercepted by the canopy. In the SEIMS model, the interception storage capacity is determined using the sine-shaped variation curve (Liu, 2004):

$$I_0 = I_{min} + (I_{max} - I_{min})[0.5 + 0.5 \sin (2\pi \cdot (d - 87) / 365)]^b \quad \text{Eq. (A. 5)}$$

Where I_0 represents the actual maximum storage capacity of the canopy (mm). I_{min} and I_{max} are the theoretical minimum and maximum interception storage capacities of the canopy (mm), determined based on vegetation type. d is the day of the year, and b is a constant. The actual interception amount per time step (I_t) and the evaporation amount (E_t) are as follows:

$$I_t = \begin{cases} I_0 - SI_{t-1}, & P_t > I_0 - SI_{t-1} \\ P_t, & P_t \leq I_0 - SI_{t-1} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 6)}$$

$$E_t = \begin{cases} 0, & SI_t = 0 \\ SI_{t-1}, & P_t = 0 \text{ and } PET > SI_{t-1} \\ PET, & \text{Else} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 7)}$$

In the equations, P_t represents the precipitation amount at the current time step (mm), SI_t and SI_{t-1} denote the interception storage amounts in the canopy at the current and previous time steps, respectively (mm), and PET is the potential evapotranspiration on the given day (mm).

1.1.4 Infiltration

The infiltration rate is a function of precipitation, land use type, soil characteristics, and antecedent soil moisture content. In the SEIMS model, the Modified Rational method (Liu, 2004) is used to estimate the amount of infiltration as follows:

$$PE_t = C \cdot (P_t - I_t) \cdot \left(\frac{\theta_t}{\theta_s}\right)^a \quad \text{Eq. (A. 8)}$$

$$F_t = P_t - I_t - PE_t \quad \text{Eq. (A. 9)}$$

In the equations, C represents the potential runoff coefficient, which is determined by factors such as topography, land use type, and soil type. P_t is the effective precipitation amount at time step t (mm), which includes net precipitation and depression storage. I_t is the canopy interception amount at time step t (mm). θ_t is the soil moisture content at time step t , and θ_s is the soil porosity ($\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$). a is an exponent related to precipitation intensity. PE_t is the rainfall excess at time step t (mm), which is the water stored in surface depression or directly contributes to surface runoff. F_t represents the infiltration (mm), which is the remaining effective precipitation after subtracting canopy interception and rainfall excess.

1.1.5 Depression filling and surface runoff

When the rainfall intensity exceeds the surface infiltration rate, the excess precipitation is stored in depressions and is later either evaporated or infiltrate to affect the soil moisture content and subsurface flow processes. In the SEIMS model, the depression storage amount is estimated using the empirical formula proposed by Linsley et al. (1982). The water balance

equation for the depression filling process can be expressed as follows:

$$SD_t = SD_{t-1} + PE_t \cdot e^{-\frac{PC}{SD_0}} - ED_t - F_t \quad \text{Eq. (A. 10)}$$

In the equation, SD_t represents the cell depression storage at time t, SD_0 is the cell depression storage capacity (mm), PE_t is the rainfall excess at the current time step (mm), and PC is the accumulated excess rainfall (mm), which is estimated using the excess rainfall at time t and the depression storage at time t-1. ED_t and F_t are evaporation and infiltration from depression storage (mm).

The model assumes that depression filling and surface runoff occur simultaneously. After rainfall, water may temporarily be stored in surface depressions or directly contribute to surface runoff. The surface runoff (R_{surf} , mm) is calculated using the following formula:

$$R_{surf} = PE_t \left(1 - e^{-\frac{PE_t}{SD_0}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. (A. 11)}$$

1.1.6 Seepage

Seepage occurs in the whole soil profile when the soil is unfrozen and the soil water content exceeds the field capacity. In the SEIMS model, the amount of seepage from the upper to the lower soil layer is referenced from Neitsch et al. (2011):

$$TT_{perc} = \frac{\theta_{sat} - FC}{k_s} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 12)}$$

$$R_{perc} = SW_{excess} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{-\Delta t}{TT_{perc}}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. (A. 13)}$$

Where R_{perc} represents the seepage amount (mm), SW_{excess} is the maximum potential seepage amount (mm), which is the difference between the soil water content and the field capacity (mm), TT_{perc} is the seepage travel time (hr), Δt is the time step (hr), θ_{sat} and FC are the soil water content at saturation and the field capacity, respectively (mm), and k_s is the saturated soil hydraulic conductivity (mm h^{-1}).

1.1.7 Subsurface flow

When the soil water content exceeds its field capacity, the excess water will move vertically downward due to gravity. Additionally, a portion of the water may generate lateral subsurface flow. In areas with impermeable or semi-permeable layers, subsurface flow generally contributes significantly to the recession process of hydrographs. While, in steep, forested, and humid regions, it may also contribute to peak flow during floods. In the SEIMS model, it is assumed that the hydraulic gradient within the simulation unit is approximately equal to the topographic slope. Subsurface flow is calculated based on Darcy's law and the kinematic wave equation (Liu et al., 2004):

$$R_{lat} = \frac{C_s \cdot D_{sol} \cdot S \cdot k_{\theta} \cdot \Delta t}{Len} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 14)}$$

Where R_{lat} is the subsurface flow (mm), C_s is the correction factor for horizontal saturated hydraulic conductivity, D_{sol} is the soil layer thickness (m), S is the average slope (m m^{-1}), k_{θ} is the hydraulic conductivity at soil water content θ (mm hr^{-1}), and Len is the flow path width (m). For grid cells, when the flow direction is parallel to the rows or columns of the grid, Len equals the grid width; when the flow direction is diagonal to the grid, Len equals the grid width divided by square root of 2. For irregular polygonal units, Len equals the shared edge length between upstream and downstream units.

The equation from Clapp and Hornberger (1978) is used to calculate the unsaturated hydraulic conductivity.

$$k_{\theta} = k_s (\theta / \theta_{sat})^{3+2/\lambda} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 15)}$$

Where k_{θ} represents the hydraulic conductivity at soil water content (mm hr^{-1}), k_s represents the saturated hydraulic conductivity, which is the maximum hydraulic conductivity of the soil when it is fully saturated (mm hr^{-1}). θ represents the current soil water content (mm), θ_{sat} represents the saturated water content. λ represents the pore size distribution index, a dimensionless parameter that describes the distribution of pore sizes in the soil.

1.1.8 Soil evaporation

In the SEIMS model, the evaporation from soil water is calculated based on the potential evaporation, vegetation, and soil water content using the following relationship (Thornthwaite et al., 1955):

$$ES_i(t) = \begin{cases} [c_v EP_i(t) - EI_i(t) - ED_i(t)] \left[\frac{M_i(t) - M_{i,w}}{M_{i,f} - M_{i,w}} \right], & M_{i,w} \leq M_i(t) < M_{i,f} \\ c_v EP_i(t) - EI_i(t) - ED_i(t), & M_i(t) \geq M_{i,f} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 16)}$$

Where $ES_i(t)$ represents the soil water evaporation within unit i during time period t (mm); $EP_i(t)$ is the potential evaporation (mm), $EI_i(t)$ is the interception evaporation (mm); $ED_i(t)$ is the depression storage evaporation (mm); c_v is the vegetation coefficient within unit i , determined by land use type; $M_i(t)$ is the soil water content (m^3/m^3); and $M_{i,f}$ and $M_{i,w}$ are the field capacity and wilting point, respectively (m^3/m^3).

1.1.9 Hillslope routing

Hillslope routing is the process of surface runoff transport to the channel. The speed of hillslope routing is usually fast, but for larger subbasins, the travel time may exceed one day. In the SEIMS model, the amount of surface runoff entering the channel at each time step is:

$$RS = (R_{surf} + R_{surf,h}) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{Surlag}{T_{surf}}}\right) \quad \text{Eq. (A. 17)}$$

Where RS represents the surface runoff routed to the channel at the current time step (mm); R_{surf} is the surface runoff generated at the current time step (mm), $R_{surf,h}$ is the remaining surface runoff that has not yet route to the channel (mm), $Surlag$ is the surface runoff lag coefficient, set by the user, and T_{surf} is the time of concentration (hours). This method ignores the actual flow pathway of surface runoff and may introduce inaccuracy in the presence of impoundments such as wetlands and ponds.

$$T_{surf} = t_{ch} + t_{ovv} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 18)}$$

$$t_{ov} = 0.0556 \times (sls \times ov_n)^{0.6} / (slp)^{0.3} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 19)}$$

$$t_{ch} = 0.62 \times ch_l \times (ch_n)^{0.75} / (A_s)^{0.125} \times (ch_s)^{0.375} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 20)}$$

Where sls is average slope length for subbasin (m), ov_n is Manning's n value for overland flow, slp is average slope of subbasin (m m^{-1}), ch_l is the longest tributary channel length in subbasin (km), ch_n is Manning's n value for the channel, A_s is the simulation unit area (km^2), ch_s is the average slope of channel (m m^{-1}).

For cases where there is an upstream-downstream relationship between basic simulation units, the subsurface flow routing is calculated according to the flow direction, and only the units adjacent to the channel contribute to the channel flow. For cases where there is no upstream-downstream relationship between basic simulation units (i.e., the downstream of all the units is assumed to be the channel), the flow path width is assumed to be the width of the simulation unit (square root of the unit area). The formula for calculating the subsurface flow entering the channel at each time step is as follows:

$$RI = (R_{lat} + R_{lat,h}) \cdot \left(1 - e^{-\frac{-1}{T_{lat}}}\right) \quad \text{Eq. (A. 21)}$$

Where RI represents the lateral flow travel to the channel at the current time step (mm), R_{lat} is the lateral flow generated at the current time step (mm), $R_{lat,h}$ is the remaining lateral flow that has not yet enter the channel (mm), and T_{lat} is the subsurface flow travel time (days), which can be specified by the user or calculated as follows:

$$T_{lat} = 10.4 \cdot \frac{L_{hill}}{k_s} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 22)}$$

Where L_{hill} represents the hillslope length (m), and k_s is the saturated hydraulic conductivity of the soil (mm hr^{-1}).

1.1.10 Soil temperature and its hydrological effects

The temperature changes in the snow and soil layer are controlled by heat conduction and latent heat exchange, where latent heat exchange is caused by the freeze-thaw cycle within the soil profile (Yin and Arp, 1993). In the SEIMS model, the soil temperature changes are calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\partial T_{soil}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{tc}{C} \cdot \frac{\partial T_{soil}}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{s}{C} \quad \text{Eq. (A.23)}$$

Where T_{soil} is the soil temperature of each layer ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), tc is the thermal conductivity ($\text{J cm}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$), and C is the volumetric heat capacity ($\text{J cm}^{-3} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$). x is the depth of the soil layer (cm), and s is the latent heat generated by the soil ice/water phase change ($\text{J cm}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$). The soil temperature of each layer is calculated based on the center point of the soil layer, and it is assumed that the heat capacity and thermal conductivity are uniform within each layer.

In the vertical direction, the upper boundary of the simulation is the snow layer (or the first soil layer), and the lower boundary is the soil damping depth, which is the depth where the influence of air temperature changes becomes negligible (set by user). When the damping depth exceeds the preset soil depth, additional soil layers (default is 5 layers) are added for soil temperature simulation. These additional soil layers have the same thermodynamic properties as the last soil layer, with the same thickness which are determined based on the damping depth.

The thermal conductivity (tc) of unsaturated soil is calculated using the method proposed by Johansen (1975):

$$tc = tc_{coe} \left[(tc_s - tc_{dry}) \cdot tc_e + tc_{dry} \right] \quad \text{Eq. (A.24)}$$

Where tc_s and tc_{dry} represent the thermal conductivity under saturated and dry conditions, respectively, with the same dry density. tc_{coe} denotes the soil thermal conductivity correction coefficient, and tc_e is the Kersten number, determined by the degree of saturation. tc is calculated using the geometric mean of the thermal conductivities of its components (water, air, or ice) and their respective volume fractions.

The decrease in soil temperature leads to an increase in the soil ice content in the winter. Ice crystals can alter the effective porosity of each soil layer, thereby affecting the soil hydraulic conductivity. In SEIMS, the coupling of water and thermal in frozen soil is optional. If user considers the impact of frozen soil on hydrology, the simulation method refers to the following equation (Niu et al., 2006):

$$frz = e^{-\alpha(1-\theta_{ice}/\theta_s)} - e^{-\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. (A.25)}$$

$$k = (1 - frz) \cdot k_s \cdot \left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_{sat}} \right)^{2b+3} \quad \text{Eq. (A.26)}$$

Where frz represents the soil freezing ratio, α ($=3$) is a constant, θ_{sat} is the saturated soil water content (mm), θ_{ice} is the ice content (mm), k and k_s are the hydraulic conductivities under current and saturated conditions, respectively (mm h^{-1}), and b is determined by soil properties.

1.1.11 Groundwater processes

The water percolates through the bottom layer of the soil recharges the shallow aquifer, and some may enter the deep aquifer. The water in the deep aquifer is not considered in the watershed's water balance. Groundwater outflow occurs when the water storage capacity of shallow aquifers exceeds the user-defined threshold, and it is calculated using the following equation in the SEIMS model (Liu et al., 2004):

$$Q_g = c_g \cdot \left(\frac{SG_t}{1000} \right)^m \quad \text{Eq. (A. 27)}$$

Where Q_g is the groundwater outflow ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), c_g is a groundwater recession coefficient taking the subbasin area into account, with a dimension of ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) for linear reservoir and ($\text{m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) for non-linear reservoir, SG_t is the groundwater storage at this time step (mm), m is the baseflow coefficient, when $m = 1$, it represents a linear reservoir, and when $m \neq 1$, it represents a non-linear reservoir.

Water can return to the soil layer from shallow aquifer through evaporation, and the evaporation amount depends on the difference between the average potential evapotranspiration and the actual evaporation of the subbasin:

$$E_{gw} = (PET - AET) \cdot \frac{SG_t}{SG_{max}} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 28)}$$

Where PET is the potential evapotranspiration (mm), AET is the actual evaporation (mm), SG_{max} is the maximum water storage capacity of aquifer which is set by the user (mm).

1.1.12 Channel routing processes

The SEIMS model uses the Muskingum method to simulate channel routing processes. The Muskingum method is a channel routing algorithm based on the storage equation and the water balance equation. The basic equation is as follows:

$$Q_{out,2} = C_1 Q_{in,2} + C_2 Q_{in,1} + C_3 Q_{out,1} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 29)}$$

Where $Q_{out,2}$ is the river outflow at the end of the time step ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), $Q_{out,1}$ is the river outflow at the beginning of the time step ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), $Q_{in,2}$ is the river inflow at the end of the time step ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), $Q_{in,1}$ is the river inflow at the beginning of the time step ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are the weighting coefficients, and their sum is 1, and the calculation methods of these

coefficients are as follows:

$$C_1 = \frac{\Delta t - 2KX}{2K(1 - X) + \Delta t} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 30)}$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\Delta t + 2KX}{2K(1 - X) + \Delta t} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 31)}$$

$$C_3 = \frac{2K(1 - X) - \Delta t}{2K(1 - X) + \Delta t} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 32)}$$

In the equation, K is the storage coefficient, which is the river segment propagation time under steady flow conditions (h). X is the weighting factor that controls the river outflow and inflow (0~0.5).

1.2 Soil erosion

1.2.1 Hillslope erosion

In the SEIMS model, the total amount of sediment produced by slope erosion is calculated using the Modified Universal Soil Loss Equation (MUSLE) (Neitsch et al., 2011):

$$SED = 11.8 \cdot (Q_s \cdot q_{peak} \cdot A)^{0.56} \cdot K \cdot C \cdot P \cdot LS \cdot CFRG \quad \text{Eq. (A. 33)}$$

Where SED represents the sediment yield in erosion (t) on a given day, Q_s denotes the surface runoff (m^3), q_{peak} indicates the peak flow rate ($m^3 s^{-1}$), A signifies the simulated unit area (m^2). The soil erodibility factor, K , depends on the structure of soil particles and the organic carbon content. C is the cover and management factor (dimensionless), influenced by the type of land cover; for instance, the value for grassland is typically lower than that for farmland. P is the USLE support practice factor (dimensionless), and LS is the topographic factor (dimensionless). Additionally, $CFRG$ represents the coarse fragment factor.

1.2.2 Channel sediment transport

The sediment transport dynamics in river channels or reaches involve two processes: deposition and degradation. The dominant mechanism is determined by the relationship between the concentration of sediment in the reach and the maximum amount of sediment that can be transported from a reach segment. Specifically, deposition prevails when sediment concentration exceeds the maximum transport capacity, while degradation dominates under sub-capacity conditions (Neitsch et al., 2011). The maximum amount of sediment that can be transported from a reach segment exhibits functional dependence on the peak channel velocity.

$$v_{ch,pk} = \frac{prf \cdot q_{ch}}{A_{ch}} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 34)}$$

$$conc_{max} = c_{sp} \cdot v_{ch,pk}^{spexp} \quad \text{Eq. (A.35)}$$

Where $v_{ch,pk}$ is the peak channel velocity of the river (m s^{-1}), prf is the peak rate adjustment factor, q_{ch} is the average rate of flow ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), A_{ch} is the cross-sectional area of flow (m^2), $conc_{max}$ is the maximum concentration of sediment that can be transported by the water (ton m^{-3}), c_{sp} is the constant coefficient, and $spexp$ is the user-defined exponent, which usually varies between 1 and 2, with a default value of 1.5 in the original Bagnoldstream power equation.

The net amount of sediment deposited and re-suspended is calculated using the following formula:

$$sed_{dep} = (conc_{sed,ch,i} - conc_{sed,ch,mx}) \cdot V_{ch} \quad \text{Eq. (A.36)}$$

$$sed_{deg} = (conc_{sed,ch,mx} - conc_{sed,ch,i}) \cdot V_{ch} \cdot K_{ch} \cdot C_{ch} \quad \text{Eq. (A.37)}$$

Where sed_{dep} is the amount of sediment deposited in the reach segment (ton), $conc_{sed,ch,i}$ is the initial sediment concentration of the river channel (ton m^{-3}), $conc_{sed,ch,mx}$ is the maximum sediment concentration that can be transported by the river channel (ton m^{-3}), V_{ch} is the amount of water in the river channel (m^3), sed_{deg} is the amount of sediment reentrained in the reach segment (ton), K_{ch} is the channel erodibility factor ($\text{cm hr}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-1}$), which is typically one order of magnitude smaller than the soil erodibility factor, and C_{ch} is the channel cover factor, defined as the ratio of degradation from a channel with a specified vegetative cover to the corresponding degradation with no vegetative cover.

1.3 Terrestrial carbon cycling processes

1.3.1 Vegetation growth

The vegetation growth module in the SEIMS model implements the Environmental Policy Integrated Climate (EPIC) model framework (Williams et al., 1984), which simulates growth dynamics across vegetation types (e.g., annual crops and perennial trees) through a process-driven approach. The core algorithm integrates radiation-use efficiency (RUE) theory with environmental stress response mechanisms. Vegetation parameters are species-specific via lookup tables, while management practices (e.g., irrigation, fertilization) are user customized. Daily potential biomass accumulation (Δbio) is calculated using RUE :

$$\Delta bio = RUE \cdot H_{phosyn} \quad \text{Eq. (A.38)}$$

Where H_{phosyn} (MJ m^{-2}) represents daily intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), derived from Beer's law:

$$H_{phosyn} = 0.5 \cdot H_{day} \cdot (1 - \exp(-k_l \cdot LAI)) \quad \text{Eq. (A.39)}$$

Where H_{day} is total incident solar radiation (MJ/m²), $0.5 \cdot H_{day}$ represents PAR, k_l is the light extinction coefficient, and LAI is the leaf area index. Actual biomass production (Δbio_{act}) incorporates environmental stress factors:

$$\Delta bio_{act} = \Delta bio \cdot \gamma_{reg} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 40)}$$

The growth regulation factor (γ_{reg}) integrates water ($wstrs$), temperature ($tstrs$), nitrogen ($nstrs$), and phosphorus ($pstrs$) stresses:

$$\gamma_{reg} = 1 - \max(wstrs, tstrs, nstrs, pstrs) \quad \text{Eq. (A. 41)}$$

Additionally, the EPIC model employs a thermal time accumulation method to track plant developmental stages, from emergence to maturity. Key phenological events, such as emergence, senescence, and dormancy, are triggered when accumulated growing degree days reach species-specific thresholds. For dry matter allocation, potential heat units (PHU) combined with optimal leaf area development curves to simulate the dynamic changes in canopy height and leaf area index (LAI). The LAI trajectory follows a sigmoidal (S-shaped) curve, capturing slow initial growth, rapid mid-phase expansion, and late-phase stabilization. The root-to-total biomass ratio varies significantly throughout the growing period, with an initial allocation coefficient of 0.40 during the emergence stage that linearly decreases to 0.20 at maturity. This reflects the plant's strategic shift from prioritizing resource capture (root growth) to reproductive allocation (aboveground biomass). Together, these mechanisms enable the EPIC model to effectively simulate vegetation growth dynamics under varying environmental conditions and management practices, providing a robust framework for assessing plant responses to stressors and interventions.

1.3.2 Soil carbon cycling

In the SEIMS model, the soil carbon cycle module simulates soil organic carbon (SOC) dynamics based on the CENTURY model developed by Zhang et al. (2013). This model integrates the synergistic regulation mechanism of carbon pool turnover time and carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (C: N), classifying SOC into five functional pools: structural litter carbon (LSC; e.g., lignin and cell walls), metabolic litter carbon (LMC; e.g., proteins and sugars), microbial biomass carbon (BMC), slow-turnover humus carbon (HSC; turnover time of approximately 400–2000 years), and passive humus carbon (HPC; turnover time of approximately 200–1500 years).

The dynamic changes in carbon pools follow the principle of mass conservation, with their rates of change determined by the net effect of carbon inputs and decomposition losses. This process can be described by the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = I - k \times CS \times x \quad \text{Eq. (A. 42)}$$

Where x represents the size of the carbon pool (kg C ha⁻¹); t denotes time (days); I is the input rate of the carbon pool (kg C ha⁻¹); k is the rate constant for carbon degradation per unit carbon pool under ideal conditions (kg C ha⁻¹); and CS is a dimensionless factor representing the influence of soil environmental conditions (e.g., soil temperature, soil moisture, oxygen availability, and soil texture) on organic carbon decomposition.

The distribution mechanisms and decomposition processes of carbon within the soil can be summarized as follows. First, the allocation of plant residue input is the initial stage of the carbon cycle. The distribution of residue carbon between LSC and LMC pools is determined based on the relationship between lignin content and C:N ratio, calculated as:

$$LMF = 0.85 - 0.013 \times \frac{\text{lignin content}}{N \text{ content}} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 43)}$$

Where the proportion of residue carbon allocated to the LMC pool (LMF) is typically greater than 0.2, and the remaining residue carbon ($1 - LMF$) is allocated to the LSC pool (Parton et al., 1987).

Second, during the decomposition and metabolism processes, the degradation of both litter and SOC is accompanied by CO₂ mineralization and the transfer of carbon to other pools. Specifically, when the LSC pool decomposes, a portion of carbon is lost as CO₂ through microbial respiration, while the remaining carbon is proportionally distributed to the BMC and HSC pools. In contrast, the decomposition products of the LMC pool, apart from CO₂, are entirely transferred to the BMC pool after mineralization. The kinetics of these processes can be quantified using the following decomposition rate equations, while additional calculation formulas can be found in the appendix of Zhang et al. (2013):

$$k_{LSC} = LSC \times LSR \times \exp(-3 \times LSLF) \times CS \quad \text{Eq. (A. 44)}$$

$$k_{LMC} = LMC \times LMR \times CS \quad \text{Eq. (A. 45)}$$

Where LSC and LMC represent the lignin content in the LSC and LMC litter carbon pools (kg C ha⁻¹); LSR and LMR denote the optimal decomposition rates of LSC and LMC (kg C ha⁻¹); and $LSLF$ represents the lignin fraction in the LSC litter (dimensionless).

1.3.3. Soil DOC leaching

In the SEIMS model, it is assumed that the amount of DOC in the soil depends on the microbial biomass pool, and the amount of DOC leaching in the soil solution (DOC_{mass} , kg ha⁻¹) is calculated as follows (Du et al., 2019):

$$DOC_{mass} = (1 - e^{[-w_{mobile}/AWC + k_{doc} \cdot SOC \cdot 10^{-4}]}) \cdot SOL_{BMC} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 46)}$$

Where SOL_{BMC} (kg ha^{-1}) is the amount of microbial biomass in a soil layer; kd_{oc} is the liquid-solid partition coefficient for microbial biomass; SOC (kg ha^{-1}) is the total amount of organic carbon in a certain soil layer; w_{mobile} (mm) is the amount of mobile water in each soil layer, including the amount of lateral transport (surface runoff and subsurface flow) and vertical transport (percolation), and AWC (mm) is the soil available water content.

The DOC concentration of the mobile water for a given layer can be expressed as:

$$DOC_{con,mobile} = DOC_{mass} \cdot \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[\frac{-w_{mobile}}{(1 - \theta_s) \cdot \theta_{sat}} \right] \right\} / w_{mobile} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 47)}$$

Where θ_s represents the soil porosity in fraction, and θ_{sat} denotes the saturated water content of the soil layer (mm). The amount of DOC lost due to mobile water in each soil layer is calculated based on the total volume and the DOC concentration of mobile water.

DOC is recharged into the shallow aquifer through the bottom of the soil column. A portion of the DOC in the shallow aquifer enters the channel with groundwater, while the remaining DOC in the shallow aquifer would be lost due to biological and chemical reactions:

$$DOC_{sh,t} = (DOC_{sh,t0} + DOC_{perc,lowest} - DOC_{gw}) \cdot e^{kgw} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 48)}$$

$$DOC_{gw} = \frac{DOC_{sh,t0} + DOC_{perc,lowest}}{S_{sh,t} + E_{gw} + R_{gw}} \cdot R_{gw} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 49)}$$

Where $DOC_{sh,t}$ (kg ha^{-1}) and $DOC_{sh,t0}$ (kg ha^{-1}) represent the final and initial amounts of DOC in shallow aquifers at a given time step, respectively; $DOC_{perc,lowest}$ (kg ha^{-1}) and DOC_{gw} (kg ha^{-1}) are the amounts of DOC recharged to the shallow aquifer at the bottom of the soil column and the amount of DOC exported through groundwater flow, respectively; kgw is the rate constant for DOC reactions in the shallow aquifer (day^{-1}); and $S_{sh,t0}$ (mm), E_{gw} (mm) and R_{gw} (mm) are the final water volume, groundwater evaporation, and groundwater flow of the shallow aquifer at a given time step, respectively.

1.3.4 POC loss

In the SEIMS model, the POC loss via erosion is calculated as based on the soil erosion ratio, SOC concentration in surface soil and the enrichment ratio (Zhang et al., 2018).

$$POC_{sed} = \frac{SED}{SOL_{mass}} \cdot SOC \cdot ERPOC \quad \text{Eq. (A. 50)}$$

Where POC_{sed} is the eroded POC yield (kg ha^{-1}) of the current time step, SED represents the sediment yield in erosion (kg), SOL_{mass} is the soil mass (kg); SOC (kg ha^{-1}) is the total amount of organic carbon in a certain soil layer; and $ERPOC$ is the POC enrichment rate (0-1) defined as the ratio of POC in the eroded sediment to the total organic carbon in the soil surface layer, which is defined by the user.

1.4 Aquatic carbon cycling processes

In the SEIMS model, the riverine DOC simulation combines the QUAL2K (Chapra et al., 2003) and CE-QUAL-W2 (Cole and Wells, 2006) model, where DOC flux dynamics are governed by mass balance principles: DOC increase floating and bottom algae mortality, and POC dissolution, while DOC decrease is driven by nitrate denitrification process consumption and mineralization by aquatic microorganisms (Du et al., 2019):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C_{DOC}}{\partial t} = & F_{DOCp} \cdot k_{dp} \cdot r_{ca} \cdot A_p + k_{POC} \cdot C_{POC} + \frac{1}{h} F_{DOCb} \cdot k_{db} \cdot r_{cb} \cdot A_b - F_{oxc} \cdot k_{DOC} \cdot C_{DOC} \\ & - r_{CN} \cdot (1 - F_{oxdn}) \cdot k_{dnit} \cdot NO_3 \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 51)}$$

Where C_{DOC} is the DOC concentration in the channel (mg L^{-1}), F_{DOCp} is the fraction of floating algae mortality to DOC (0-1), k_{dp} is the floating algae mortality rate (day^{-1}), r_{ca} is the ratio of carbon to algal biomass ($\text{mg C mg}^{-1} \text{D}$), A_p is the floating algae biomass (mg D L^{-1}), k_{POC} is the dissolution rate of POC to DOC (day^{-1}), C_{POC} represents the POC concentration (mg L^{-1}), h is the depth of the river (m), F_{DOCb} is the fraction of bottom algae mortality to DOC (0-1), k_{db} is the rate of bottom algae mortality (day^{-1}), r_{cb} is the ratio of carbon to bottom algae biomass ($\text{mg C mg}^{-1} \text{D}$), A_b is the biomass of bottom algae (g D m^{-2}), F_{oxc} represents the attenuation of DOC oxidation under hypoxic conditions (dimensionless), and k_{DOC} is the mineralization rate of DOC (day^{-1}), r_{CN} is the carbon to nitrogen ratio, F_{oxdn} is the enhancement coefficient of denitrification at low oxygen concentration (dimensionless), k_{dnit} is the denitrification rate (day^{-1}), and NO_3 is the nitrate concentration in the water column (mg N L^{-1}). Among them, the photosynthesis, respiration, and mortality processes for both floating and bottom algae are simulated using the QUAL2K model.

Similarly, POC fluxes exhibit source-sink dynamics: increase by floating and bottom algae mortality, while reduced through dissolution, mineralization by microorganisms, settling, and downstream export (Qi et al., 2020):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial C_{POC}}{\partial t} = & F_{POCp} \cdot k_{dp} \cdot r_{ca} \cdot A_p + \frac{1}{h} F_{POCb} \cdot k_{db} \cdot r_{cb} \cdot A_b - k_{POC,dec} \cdot C_{POC} - k_{POC} \cdot C_{POC} \\ & - \frac{V_{POC}}{h} \cdot C_{POC} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. (A. 52)}$$

Where C_{POC} is the POC concentration (mg L^{-1}), F_{POCp} is the fraction of floating algae mortality to POC (0-1), F_{POCb} is the fraction of bottom algae mortality to POC (0-1), $k_{POC,dec}$ is the mineralization rate of POC (day^{-1}), V_{POC} is the POC settling velocity (m day^{-1}), and other parameters as same as described in the DOC model framework.

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